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Mapping the Body: Developing Body Maps as Research Tool to Derive Quantifiable and Context-Sensitive Design Insights

AMAR D'ADAMO, Carlos III University of Madrid, Getafe, Madrid, Spain

LAIA TURMO VIDAL, KTH Royal Institute of Technology, Stockholm, Stockholms, Sweden

KARUNYA SRINIVASAN, Carlos III University of Madrid, Getafe, Madrid, Spain

MOHAMMAD MAHDI DEHSHIBI, Carlos III University of Madrid, Getafe, Madrid, Spain

DANIEL DE LA PRIDA, Technical University of Madrid, Madrid, Madrid, Spain

ANA TAJADURA JIMÉNEZ, Carlos III University of Madrid, Getafe, Madrid, Spain

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Mapping the Body: Developing Body Maps as Research Tool to Derive Quantifiable and Context-Sensitive Design Insights

Amar D'Adamo

Universidad Carlos III de Madrid
Madrid, Spain
4m4r000@gmail.com

Laia Turmo Vidal

KTH Royal Institute of Technology
Stockholm, Sweden
laiatv@kth.se

Karunya Srinivasan

Universidad Carlos III de Madrid
Madrid, Spain
ksriniva@inf.uc3m.es

Mohammad Mahdi Dehshibi

Universidad Carlos III de Madrid
Madrid, Spain
mohammad.dehshibi@yahoo.com

Daniel De La Prida

Universidad Politécnica de Madrid
Madrid, Spain
daniel.prida@upm.es

Ana Tajadura Jiménez

Universidad Carlos III de Madrid
Madrid, Spain
University College London
London, United Kingdom
atajadur@inf.uc3m.es

Figure 1: a) Classic body map; b) Study 1: body maps, first colored by a participant and then segmented in 136 regions; c) Study 2: one of the experimenters tracking the participants route in the landscape map; d) Study 2: view from above of the experiment area showing the different zones in which participants could walk while synchronizing to the prerecorded footsteps sounds.

Abstract

Researching body experiences poses challenges due to their inherently subjective and intangible nature. In TEI, more broadly in HCI, methods like body maps capture these experiences. We advance body maps by developing and applying two extensions to body maps to address important dimensions of body experience. These were tested in two studies. The first focuses on design processes aimed at achieving more generalizable data through quantitative methods, while enabling analysis from an individual perspective. Here, we introduce a segmentation approach of body maps for quantifying and comparing body experiences. These maps feature subdivisions of various body areas, derived from a study reporting the effects of movement sonification intervention on body perception. The segmentation allows for precise measurement and comparison of these changes. In the second, we shift to the context in which body experiences take place, presenting context-sensitive body maps anchored in the environment. These maps explore the

relationship between body and environment. We present methodologies for researching embodied interactions within TEI.

CCS Concepts

• Human-centered computing → HCI design and evaluation methods.

Keywords

Body Maps; Documentation Tools; Experimental Methods; Evaluation Methods; Embodied Interaction; Sonification; Wearable Computers

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1 Introduction

Our body experience is a phenomenon involving both perceptual (e.g., perceived body size) and attitudinal (e.g., emotional responses and thoughts towards body size) components [18] that impact motor [9], emotional [52, 57], and social functioning [5, 10, 61]. The

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way we perceive our body is dynamic and updates in response to different stimuli and contexts [14]. Researching body experiences is difficult due to their intrinsically personal and elusive character [72]. In experimental psychology and related disciplines, changes in body perception are mostly assessed by employing quantitative approaches. These include questionnaires [41], behavioral measures [6, 69], and/or measures of physiological changes consistent with the altered perception [3]. Human Computer Interaction (HCI) has employed and proposed multiple methods to allow for nuanced access and articulation of felt body experiences [29, 44, 72, 81]. One such method, body maps [2, 71], has been widely employed as a tool to help elicit and capture participants' body experiences qualitatively. Body maps offer an abstracted, empty silhouette representing the body within which people represent their felt bodily sensations. Body maps not only serve to measure or compare sensations, but also to respect and foreground the inherently personal, situated, and affective qualities of bodily perception—emphasizing the subjective nature of human bodily experience. In HCI, they are often used to derive rich accounts to be used in design and research [2, 71]. However, current implementations of body maps in interaction design present limitations. First, they are predominantly used in qualitative studies, and their capacity to be used in quantitative analyses to produce generalizable or reproducible data for broader analysis is yet underexplored in our field.

Second, the traditional body map silhouettes are often context-neutral, failing to account for the dynamic and situated nature of body experiences as they occur in real-world interactions [71]. These shortcomings limit their potential to explore the intricate relationship between our bodies and the environment, and how they mutually co-constitute each other.

In this paper, we address emerging interest in TEI, and more broadly HCI, in developing more flexible and context-aware methods for studying body experiences, as well as methods that bridge subjective experience with structured, generalizable insights about body perception. We propose to advance body maps by addressing two important dimensions of body experience: where we perceive bodily changes, and how external environmental contexts shape those perceptions. To do this, we present two studies that develop and apply extensions to body maps. Study 1 focuses on structuring where in the body sensations are experienced; we illustrate this approach with a study that employs auditory feedback with the potential to change body perceptions and related sensations. Study 2 looks outwards to address the contextual factors that influence body perceptions, and in particular investigates how these body experiences are shaped by environmental and contextual factors during real-world movement. While the studies differ in focus and methodology, they are united by their aim to expand the methodological and analytical potential of body maps in body perception research, fostering bodily awareness, sensitivity, and reflection as central dimensions of interaction design practice.

Based on the work in two studies that centered on exploring how body sonification affects one's own body image, capabilities, and emotions, here, we advance body maps as a tool for interaction designers in two key ways. First, we present segmented body maps as a novel tool for quantitative analyses. The segmented body maps present a nuanced sub-division of body areas both into micro- and macro-segments, and can be used for deriving quantitative and

generalizable design insights involving body experiences. Drawing from psychology traditions [32, 48, 53, 56, 58] that employ body maps in experimental studies, we introduce *segmented body maps*, a methodological tool geared towards quantitative studies to quantify and compare felt changes in body perception. In particular, our body map presents divisions and subdivisions of multiple body areas. This partitioning was derived based on an experimental study (Study 1) investigating the effects of sonification on body perception [13], in which 84 participants from different populations were asked to mark on a classic body map where in the body they felt changes in their body perception when listening to their own footstep sounds altered with a filter that enhances high frequencies (resembling sounds consistent with those produced by a lighter body), or a filter that enhances low frequencies (resulting in sounds consistent with those produced by a heavier body). Based on an analysis of the corpus of the body maps in that study and inspired by anatomical notions [8], we developed a segmentation of the body map that allowed us to quantify and compare felt changes in body perception.

We are also advancing body maps as a tool to explore the relationship between body and environment. We introduce the joint use of body maps together with landscape maps (graphical representations of the built and natural landscape)—allowing the overlapping of the two to capture snapshots of body experiences in particular landscapes. We created and tested these body maps in the context of an outdoor-qualitative study (Study 2). Building upon recent work on contextualizing somatic experiences [26, 71], the second study investigates the influence of auditory feedback and environmental context on body perception, though only focusing on immediate contextual factors with emphasis on physical environment, but not historical, political context. In Study 2, 28 participants individually walked freely in an outdoor area while listening to prerecorded filtered footstep sounds, replicating the auditory manipulations used in Study 1. In Study 2, after walking, participants were asked to fill in body map stickers and place them on the relevant part of a landscape map of the walking region that corresponded to their bodily sensations during the experience. This approach allows for a deeper understanding of how body experiences are shaped by environmental interactions, expanding on existing research on body mapping and embodied experiences in HCI (e.g., [2, 29, 44, 71, 73, 78, 81]). By incorporating environmental context, this study emphasizes the dynamic and evolving nature of body perception within real-world settings.

In this paper, we focus on the methodological contribution and application of segmented body maps, and on the development and use of body maps in context, reflecting on the type of analyses it can support and providing examples of the type of results that they can yield.

Both for body maps employed in experimental studies [32, 48, 53, 56, 58], and for those approaches exploring how body perception changes with context [26, 71], our contributions respond to the need for methodological tools that enable both fine-grained, quantifiable insights into body perception [31], and a deeper understanding of how context and environment shape those perceptions [82]. These also support TEI community's recent interest in the field, i.e., [47] and [71]. Our two contributions help expand the versatility of body maps for interaction design: the segmented body maps can allow deriving quantitative and generalizable insights in interaction

design processes. The superposition of body maps with landscape maps offer a way to capture the contextual relationship between bodies and environment, and how it affects our body experience.

2 Related Work and Context

2.1 Prior Work on Body Maps

2.1.1 Qualitative vs Quantitative Approaches. Body maps are increasingly used as a soma-based [30] and participatory research tool to explore, represent, and design for bodily experience. They allow to explore and promote self-awareness, identifying patterns, and translating experience into physical design in diverse contexts [2, 71]. The use of body maps in research offers valuable insights, helping people describe and represent their somatic sensations and emotions directly on a body outline—capturing tacit, felt, and spatial aspects of experience that are difficult to verbalize [2, 47]. Researchers use them both analytically, to study how technologies affect bodily awareness or comfort [47, 76], pain and discomfort [17] and generatively, to inspire the placement and qualities of on-body interfaces, wearables, and haptic systems [11]. Recent work has emphasized making body maps more inclusive—accounting for diverse bodies and subjective experiences—to strengthen their role as a creative method in body-centric design [71]. Nevertheless, there are practical considerations to take into account when considering large-scale studies. For example, creating body maps through long interviews or sessions [2, 75] may not always be feasible, especially when considering the type of knowledge we aim to obtain from such interviews. While body maps are relatively inexpensive to produce, the time required for in-depth sessions might not align with the goals of certain studies. Quantitative analysis, in particular, can help researchers identify patterns and trends that might not be immediately apparent through qualitative methods alone. Moreover, employing these methods in large studies allows for a broader generalization of findings, enhancing the robustness and reliability of the results. By complementing qualitative approaches with quantitative tools, we can uncover correlations and relationships that might otherwise go unnoticed, offering a more comprehensive view of body-related phenomena.

2.1.2 Quantitative approaches to Body Maps in HCI: Drawing from Psychology and Healthcare Research. Empirical studies have shown that body maps provide an effective means of capturing and representing individuals' perceptions and experiences of their bodies. In those, body maps are frequently utilized to understand emotional states, body image, and the somatic aspects of mental health conditions. For example, studies employ body maps and use quantitative methods to analyze them to investigate perceptions of touch [60], revealing gender differences and consistency with observational research. In this study 1368 participants colored body regions on silhouettes to indicate where each member of their social network could touch them. Successive strokes increased the opacity of the color, and the data were clustered using *k*-means [83] to create relationship-dependent touch-area maps. Similarly, a study by [53] with 833 participants asked them to paint body areas where they felt sensations related to different types of love. Additionally, [48] had 773 participants color body areas activated or deactivated by

emotional stimuli, and analyzed the resulting data using hierarchical clustering. All of these studies used the emBODY tool [48] and the data was collected through a visual representation (coloring the blank body map). In [19], body drawings with pain localization were digital quantified to facilitate fine-grain comparisons of human pain anatomy across disease diagnoses, to support treatment evaluation.

While these studies have primarily focused on psychological and healthcare contexts, body maps can also provide valuable insights for HCI research. By quantitatively capturing bodily sensations, touch preferences, and affective responses, researchers can inform the design of on-body interfaces, wearables, and embodied interactive systems [84]. Quantitative analysis allows scalable comparisons across participants and populations, which is critical for designing inclusive and effective technologies. Emerging methodological approaches to quantitative body maps in HCI combine data-driven analysis and interactive visualization to make visible subtle, non-observable aspects of bodily experience of dancers [12]. Informed by soma design, these methods bridge experiential and computational perspectives, offering fine-grained, expressive ways to study and represent embodiment. Moreover, recent works have focused on machine learning methods to extract pain localization [7, 22]. However, while these advances illustrate possible quantitative approaches potential, broader adoption in HCI remains underdeveloped. Quantitative body mapping could, for instance, enable the systematic comparison of embodied experiences across users or contexts, support the design of adaptive systems that respond to real-time bodily states, and help validate qualitative insights from somaesthetic through measurable patterns.

2.1.3 Capturing Body Perception and Its Dynamic Changes. Assessing body perception remains a challenging task due to its subjective and multifaceted nature. A variety of methods have been used to capture body perception, each with its strengths and limitations. Subjective reports [41], behavioral measures [6, 69], and physiological changes [3], are usually employed in experimental research. Each of these methods offers unique insights into bodily experiences. In Study 1, see [13], in addition to using these methods, participants were asked to color areas of their body where they felt changes, allowing for a personalized and dynamic representation of their body perception. This approach contrasts with previous studies, i.e., [54], where participants were asked to outline body concerns on a manikin and the interior of a predetermined shape was automatically filled in. While this method is effective for capturing broad body concerns, it may miss the specificity and subjectivity that participants intend to convey. In the approach presented here, we focus on how participants perceive and engage with their own bodies, enabling them to express their concerns directly and actively by coloring blank body silhouettes. This method allows for a more personalized representation of felt body sensations, as it avoids the potential generalization of the sensation in predetermined regions, present in pre-filled figures. The need for extracting the specific section of the body where sensations are felt is pivotal for the understanding and purpose of many quantitative analyses, e.g., [48, 53, 60]. By addressing changes in body perception through an expressive tool, the proposed use of segmented body maps, this multi-level analytical framework enhances the versatility of body

maps for research, allowing for both in-depth analysis of specific body regions and broader interpretations of overall body image perception. Despite their extensive use in psychology and healthcare, quantitative body maps remain underutilized in HCI. Adopting these approaches could bridge the gap between subjective bodily experience and design-oriented research, providing insights for the design and evaluation of tangible body-centric technology.

2.2 Body and Space: Contextualizing Body Experience

2.2.1 Context and Body Perception. In HCI, the dynamic interaction of user attributes, surrounding elements, and the particular tasks that define somatic experiences is referred to as context [20, 46]. This contextual complexity is crucial to understanding how body perception evolves in real-world settings, as external stimuli and individual differences can significantly alter bodily experiences [18, 63]. Soma-based design, a methodology within HCI, emphasizes the importance of bodily experiences in the design process. It involves engaging with the body's sensations to inform and inspire design decisions, aiming to create systems that resonate with users' embodied experiences [30]. The design and use of body maps are influenced by the context in which they are applied: while traditional body maps provide a blank, decontextualized silhouette for documenting felt sensations, these tools often abstract the body from the factors that influence its experiences [71]. In soma-based design, body maps serve as generative tools, allowing users to express and reflect upon their bodily experiences, thereby informing the design of interactive systems that align with users' somatic perceptions [2]. Prior research has applied body maps to better reflect the situated nature of somatic experiences. For example, the work by [39] explored how modifying body maps to depict bodies engaged in specific movements can more effectively extract bodily experiences in their corresponding actions. Additionally, research by [42] describes how environments—whether oppressive, liberating, or precarious—physically shape experiences of the body, revealing that embodied knowledge and lived experiences are deeply influenced by these external factors. Moreover, research by [45] highlights the relationships that individuals have with their bodies (their hair) and the way they navigate or are shaped by their surroundings. Together, these works point out that individuals can visually express how their bodies have been shaped by and continue to interact with the social, political, and historical context surrounding them, grounding them in their specific, present, and physical environments. Similarly, [26] emphasized contextualizing body maps within narrative frameworks, i.e., storytelling methodologies, integrating environmental, social, and temporal elements. These approaches provide a richer understanding of how external factors influence bodily sensations and emotions.

2.2.2 Maps to Document Body Experience in the Environment. Mapping techniques play a pivotal role in analyzing body interactions within specific contexts. Research in HCI has examined how the environment influences bodily experiences. For instance, [67] designed a wearable device that captures and amplifies the sound of footsteps, highlighting the interplay between a walker and their urban environment. The device encourages users to interact with various surfaces—i.e., metal grates, gravel, and marble steps—to

transform walking into an exploratory and auditory experience. Similarly, in the work by [34], participants followed maps of city areas on foot to explore auditory paths created by the acoustic properties of different urban materials. A similar approach is used in soundwalks, where participants follow a route on a map, make stops to listen to the environment, and rate their auditory experience [80]. In contrast, the work we present here did not focus on environmental sounds but rather on artificially induced sound of walking steps: either as feedback loop from the own steps sounds (as in Study 1) or prerecorded (as in Study 2). While all these works emphasize the dynamic relationship between body, sound, and space, revealing new dimensions of how we experience the environment, the work we present specifically focuses on how sounds influence body perception. Moreover, research has looked into the evolution of somatic experiences over time when using sonification technology [73]. In contrast, Study 2 explores these experiences not only as they change over time, but also how they are perceived across in relation to space—taking into account environmental factors. Inspired by [4], that utilized outdoor area maps to document, analyze, and design interactions within residential areas where they were testing interactive play installations, we use both body maps and the outdoor Study 2 area maps (landscape maps), to capture felt sensations in specific areas of the body and areas of the space while interacting with contextual elements that shape and enrich body perception (e.g., flooring/surface material, weather/temperature, social factors). We developed and evaluated this concept in a second use case (Study 2). The approach we present highlights the importance of mapping techniques to document and analyze the dynamic interplay between the body, its sensations and the surrounding environment, supported by the experimental apparatus and measures employed.

2.3 Soma-Based Design and Embodied Interaction

Research in soma-based design and embodied interaction has expanded the ways bodily experience informs interactive system design. Studies have explored embodied ideation toolkits and movement-based sketching for design [78], and soma-driven enhancements to traditional practices, such as martial arts [43]. Soma co-designed technologies have also been applied to wellbeing and sensory engagement [23], highlighting how user-centered embodied experiences can guide the design of interactive systems. Together, these studies illustrate the growing relevance of soma-based approaches in HCI, providing design insights grounded in bodily awareness, affect, and spatial interaction. Integrating soma-based design into HCI research enriches the understanding of users' embodied experiences. By employing body maps as generative tools, researchers can capture nuanced somatic sensations and emotions that are often difficult to articulate verbally. This approach aligns with the principles of soma-based design, which prioritize the user's bodily experiences in the design process. The iterative design of body maps, informed by user feedback and inclusive practices, enhances their effectiveness as tools for documenting and analyzing bodily experiences. As HCI continues to evolve, incorporating soma-based design methodologies can lead to more empathetic and user-centered interactive systems.

Table 1: Mean(SD) values for age, weight, height and scores on the EDEQ [49] and IPAQ [27] questionnaires for participants in each of the four 21-participant groups, defined by high or low levels of physical activity (PA) and eating disorder (ED) symptomatology. See the Supplementary Material for the criteria used in group assignment.

	LOW PA-LOW ED	LOW PA-HIGH ED	HIGH PA-LOW ED	HIGH PA-HIGH ED
Age	24.05(6.26)	23.81(4.05)	25.85(8.38)	26.57(9.28)
Weight (kg)	68.16(12.79)	63.62(10.71)	66.05(8.21)	65.19(11.01)
Height (cm)	170.9(8.29)	167.71(8.86)	170.57(8.38)	170.19(8.24)
EDEQ	0.52(0.32)	2.09(0.74)	0.56(0.35)	1.96(0.69)
IPAQ	1885(759)	2251(673)	6579(2400)	6358(2315)

3 Methodology and Methods

The proposed methodology for this work on body maps is developed to facilitate a hierarchical, scalable, and meaningful analysis approach, enabling detailed research into body perception while maintaining flexibility for broader generalizable analyses. This methodology combines empirical insights from participant data, anatomical principles for accurate segmentation, and iterative refinements to ensure precision and reliability in capturing body perception changes. Moreover, it integrates environmental features and elements to analyze the influence of context on the use and interpretation of body maps, allowing the research to extend beyond abstract and isolated settings. This comprehensive approach ensures that body maps can not only localize and quantify individual experiences with high granularity but also explore how these experiences are shaped and modulated by external factors, i.e., physical surroundings, material properties, and social interactions.

3.1 Segmented Body Maps

Building on previous research on the influence of auditory feedback on body perception [63, 65], the study presented in [13] explored the impact of sound manipulations on body image in a healthy population. From a methodological perspective, this study introduces an innovative approach of segmenting body maps to quantify changes in body perception. In the study, the potential of sound feedback to alter body perception was tested using *SoniWeight Shoes*, a device based on [63] that alters the frequency components of footstep sounds to induce body-weight illusions. Related work has shown that manipulating footstep sounds during walking induces changes in perceived body weight [63, 65]. This study involved 84 participants, individually engaged in a walking task while listening to their own footsteps in three sound conditions differing by the applied filtering: a control condition with no filtering, a filter enhancing high frequencies (HF) (i.e., sounds consistent with a lighter body), and one enhancing low frequencies (LF) (i.e., sounds consistent with a heavier body). Further, the participants were divided in four groups, based on individual differences (LOW/HIGH PA groups: divided by varying levels of physical activity (PA) and LOW/HIGH ED groups: having either low or high levels of eating disorder (ED) symptomatology—see Supplementary Material for group assignment criteria). To investigate how each sound condition and how individual differences contributed to body perception, the study introduced the use of body maps (filled after each walking trial) as a quantitative tool with the objective of evaluating whether there were anatomical patterns or areas in the body in which participants

were affected by the sound modulation conditions. To quantify the subjective experiences of body perception changes induced by the sound manipulations, we employed a novel methodological approach utilizing segmented body maps as a tool for measuring and recording these perceptual shifts.

3.1.1 Employing Body Maps. Since this was a quantitative focused study, comparing body experiences across sound conditions, segmented body maps design was driven by the need for greater precision in understanding how individuals perceive bodily sensations under different experimental conditions. Additionally, integrating the analysis across distinct groups in the population, the insights could inform the design of personalized wearable technologies for healthcare [33, 77], or self-awareness applications. Starting with a pair of blank silhouettes showing the front and the rear of the body, printed on A4 paper sheets, see Figure 1 a), participants marked changes in body sensations or perceptions on the body maps after each sound condition and repetition (i.e., two body maps for each sound condition, making a total of 504 body maps). The instructions indicated to color the areas of the body in which they felt some changes. During the experiment, without having received any specific instructions on what coloring method to use to fill in the body maps, the participants used several techniques (e.g., outlining the area with a circle, marking it with a line, coloring the area completely, or marking it with a cross).

3.1.2 Creating the Segmented Body Maps. The analysis to derive the body maps was twofold: inductive and deductive. Inductively, three researchers examined a subset of body maps to identify areas frequently marked by participants. Simultaneously, they integrated concepts from anatomy literature, thanks to the expertise of one researcher, to guide the conceptualization of meaningful partitions. This combined bottom-up (empirical data) and top-down (theoretical knowledge) approach yielded initial partitions, which were iteratively refined by examining new body maps for where participants had marked them. This iterative process aimed to address potential inconsistencies and refine the partitions for greater accuracy in sensation localization. The result of this iterative process was a division of the body maps into 136 individual regions. These regions were further organized into a hierarchical tree-like structure, enabling both fine-grained analysis of specific subregions and higher-level analysis of broader body areas. This hierarchical structure comprises three levels of detail. At the highest level, we have major body regions (i.e., upper and lower body), see Figure 2 c). The intermediate level encompasses larger areas (i.e., torso, left leg, head), see Figure 2 b). Finally, the lowest level focuses on specific

Figure 2: Body map divided in: a) 136 Regions; b) 14 Micro-Areas; c) two Macro-Areas.

body parts (i.e., nose, thumb, belly button), see Figure 2 a). As an example, subregion 29 is part of the front right leg (FRLeg) area and FRLeg, FLLeg both belong to the same major region (Lower Body), see Figure 2. This segmentation method builds on conceptual notions in anatomy and enables the very high fine-grained analysis on specific regions but also allowing a higher-level analysis on major body areas (i.e. legs). The quantitative analysis of perceived changes was performed classifying each participant’s body map based on the 136 subregions, and summing the number of filled subregions according to sound conditions.

3.1.3 Using the Segmented Body Maps for the Analysis. To segment the marked body maps into the 136 subregions, and gather the data, two researchers, in discussion with a third one, printed the segmented body maps, see Figure 2 a), on a transparent plastic sheet and while a researcher overlaid it on each filled body map, see Figure 1 b), the other marked the corresponding filled areas in an Excel table. The body map data was structured in the table with sound conditions as columns and body subregions as rows. This arrangement resulted in a matrix in which each cell represented the body map associated with a particular subregion under a specific sound condition for each participant who took part in the experiment. A Matlab (version R2022a) script was then used to fill in the areas corresponding to the other two levels of segmentation. For each of the two smaller region grouping level the value 1 was assigned to the upper-level area if at least one of the subregions within that area was colored, and the value 0 was assigned if none of the subregions were colored.

3.1.4 Statistical Analysis. A hierarchical analysis was performed: first, ANOVAs were used to analyze subregions based on sound condition, repetition, and participant identifier. Subsequently, post hoc T-tests were conducted for each significant ANOVA result. Finally, for any body region showing a significant interaction effect, the mean value (representing the mean number of times each region was filled) for each sound condition was calculated. For a visual representation the body maps were colored using the mean values, as showed in Figure 3 a). Statistical analyses were computed in R (version 4.3.1, R Core Team, 2018). Alpha levels were set to 0.05 and p-values were adjusted for multiple comparisons. Comparisons involved mixed model ANOVAs with follow-up T-tests for the comparisons of interest, applying a Bonferroni correction. Note that, since the focus of this paper is not on the effects of sound

on body perception, but rather on the specific methodological use of body maps to investigate these effects, the detailed statistical results are provided in the Supplementary Material.

3.2 Body Experiences in Context

In HCI, context refers to the collection of factors that extend beyond the experiences or interactions influencing somatic experiences [20, 46, 71]. Specifically, in Study 2, we explore how external elements, i.e., weather, ground surface materials, other people (see [21]) may affect body perception during a walking task while listening and synchronizing to footstep sounds. The objective of this study is to identify how different environmental elements shape our body experience. We chose to adapt the traditional body maps, which represent felt sensations and emotions in an abstract and isolated manner, by incorporating them into the context that influences and shapes these experiences. While the purpose of these body maps, and their use case, is entirely grounded in the pre- and post-reflection of a bodily experience, or subject-object relation/interaction and shaped by the context in which the participant’s experience occurred, the graphical representation of body maps doesn’t capture the environment features in which the activity takes place. This study unveils the possibility to explore how these situated actions (walking, climbing stairs) and the environment contextualize body perception experience.

Study 2 is a qualitative study that investigates the effects on body perception of listening and synchronizing to prerecorded footstep sounds delivered through headphones while walking in an outdoor environment. The experience included two five-minute walking trials, one with high frequency filtered footstep sounds and the other with low frequency filtered sounds. During the trials, 28 participants, age (years) Mean(SD): 26.21(9.99), weight (kg): 66.86(11.44) and height (cm): 164.45(8.55), could individually choose their route within an outdoor area in the university campus, (see Figure 1) which was moderately large (approximately 70x90 m in size), mostly flat, normally not too crowded, and included different surface materials (e.g., grass, earth, concrete) and space functions (e.g., buildings entrances, plant-enclosed passages, stairs, metal ramps). Participants were instructed not to leave the perimeter of the area or enter the buildings. During the walking rounds, the experimenter marked the participants’ route on two (one for each experiment sound condition) A3-size printed landscape maps of the area. At the end of both trials the participants were interviewed.

Figure 3: a) Differences between sound conditions in the overall study population; b) Differences between eating disorders groups; c) Differences between physical activity groups.

Firstly, the interviewer, for each of the walking paths, made a brief summary of the route performed by the participant, showing it on the landscape map. Then, they discussed the experiences, explaining the perceived impact of sound on movement, while also considering external influences, like the environment and social factors. Participants compared the two experiences with different auditory stimuli, reflecting on similarities, differences, and how sound shaped their perceptions. Body maps stickers were used to create flexibility for participants to place them where they wanted, and to be able to create links between body experience and space. During the interview the participants were given the opportunity to place the stickers (70x70 mm in size) on the landscape map regions where they experienced corporal sensations or changes. The stickers were designed to be small enough to use several within the same landscape map and big enough to mark specific body areas. Additionally, the participants could describe and depict sensations, emotions, thoughts, postural changes or any event that occurred during the walking trials using colors, arrows, symbols, and words.

4 Results

This section presents the findings from both the segmented body maps (Study 1) and the contextualized body maps (Study 2), illustrating the distinct types of insights each methodological approach can yield.

4.1 Segmented Body Maps

Segmented body maps offer a precise description of where and to what extent the felt sensation is happening. Using the proposed hierarchical structure it was possible to extract the body perception changes at many levels. At the most detailed level, thanks to the analysis, it was possible to obtain significant results in body subregions otherwise not easily expressed by the participants with this level of nuance, or rather not considered a priori. Considering the aim of the presented study, which had, among other objectives, the personalization of wearable technology to embrace individual differences in the study population, that may be associated with specific differences in the location of the changes in the body, using these advanced body maps in between-subjects analyses, comparing effects of sound alteration in the four groups of the population (LOW/HIGH PA, LOW/HIGH ED), allowed the localization of body

sensations on different body parts for each of the population groups. Specifically, excluding the effect of sound condition, most of the changes involved in the HIGH PA group, involve the whole chest, dorsal back and partially the bottom area. While, for the LOW PA group, results showed changes in the area behind the right knee, see Figure 3 c). See statistical results in Supplementary Material. Regarding ED groups, some changes were found in the mouth area for LOW ED (not affected in HIGH ED), legs and inner arms, while for LOW ED the bottom area and the dorsal area of the back was affected by some changes, see Figure 3 b). Besides analyzing differences in body experience between the population groups, it is also possible to extract insights about participants based on individual difference variables. In this way, changes could be localized at the individual level (e.g., resulting in changes felt in a toe for a person or in a knee for another one).

The body maps, as illustrated in Figure 3 a), provide detailed representations of how sensations vary across regions of the body under the two different experimental conditions (HF/LF). The body map segmentation enabled a fine grained analysis, revealing patterns that varied significantly based on the condition and region under consideration. Regarding the HF condition, main differences are observed in the upper arm and forearm regions, suggesting that this condition elicits sensations related to manual or proximity interactions. The resulting area appears to be asymmetric, increasing sensations on one side. Regarding the LF condition, the lower body, particularly the thigh and calf regions, shows distinct activation patterns, possibly reflecting responses tied to grounding or lower-limb dynamics. Fine-grained analysis enables to find the overlapping influences of both conditions, these areas are illustrated in 3 a), b) with overlapping colors. This implies an interaction where the sensations from the two conditions were significant for both populations.

Overall, the results indicate that different sounds elicit distinct patterns of bodily sensations, with high-frequency (HF) sounds primarily activating the upper arm and forearm regions—often asymmetrically—suggesting associations with manual or proximal interactions, while low-frequency (LF) sounds tend to affect the lower body, particularly the thighs and calves, potentially reflecting lower-limb dynamics. These sensory patterns vary not only by sound condition but also across individual differences, as seen

Figure 4: a) *Study 2 area, three zones: Zone 1, Zone 3 and Zone 4;* b) *The experiment landscape map zones: (1) grass/earth, (2) concrete entrance, (3) concrete passage, (4) covered passage with trees, (5) grass, (6) tiled passage, (7) grass (slope), (8) concrete passage cafeteria, (9) building entrance/steps, (10) empty concrete passage, (11) building entrance with steps, (12) concrete floor with steps;* c) *Study 2 area: Zone 5 and Zone 9.*

in the differential responses between population groups: for example, HIGH PA participants exhibited changes across the chest, dorsal back, and bottom area, whereas LOW PA individuals showed localized changes behind the right knee. Similarly, LOW ED participants showed activation in the mouth, legs, and inner arms, while HIGH ED participants displayed changes mainly in the bottom and dorsal back regions. Importantly, some participants also experienced highly individualized sensation locations—i.e., in a toe or knee—emphasizing the utility of segmented body maps for capturing nuanced, personalized bodily responses. In summary, sounds do not lead to uniform bodily experiences but instead evoke distinct and diverse sensations depending on the type of sound and the listener’s individual characteristics.

Through segmented body maps, we were able to uncover detailed patterns of felt changes in bodily sensations that differ across population groups and experimental conditions, and highlight specific body regions that are most influenced by sound alterations and other variables.

4.2 Body Maps in Context: Interaction With the Environment

To understand and outline how the landscape affected body perception, as shown and detailed in Figure 4, the landscape map was divided into 12 different zones. During the analysis we compared the landscape maps containing body maps to the interview notes to locate the body maps in which participants described their experiences as being influenced by environmental and contextual factors. Body maps were filled by the participants using colors, symbols, and words, the meanings of which were explained verbally during the interview. Analyzing body maps required a process of decoding the information that was depicted in the silhouettes, see Figure 6. Our method allowed us to distinguish which body sensations were contextual and which were a result of the sound, as we also gave participants the option to draw and stick a body map that reflected their general experience of each sound condition.

Here we focus on the maps that related to context or an interaction between sound and context.

Some participants used the body maps to depict postures they adopted during the walking experience, some describing them in detail (e.g., the position of the back: straight, curved; movement of

the arms; and the orientation of the head: upright, lowered, or tilted). In the interview, they linked these postural changes to context, connecting the situational elements to the effects on felt sensations or emotions. For example, several marked body areas in which the ground material or the surrounding space features made them focus on those specific body areas—coloring them or drawing a circle around them—or provoked felt sensations—indicating their nature (e.g., feeling lighter, quicker, tired, stressed, calm), or sometimes adding words (e.g., "heavy", "relaxed", "violated", "straight up", "cold", "safe", "fluid"). Symbols were also used in some body maps: for example, participant P10 drew weights hanging from his feet to indicate that he felt slow and said, *Especially on the steps I felt strange because I was wearing cushioned shoes and the sound was like shoes that hit the ground and I don't know if it's because of the terrain I was walking on or the shoes I was wearing but it didn't seem plausible at all. This made me feel even slower.*

Through the overlap of the two maps (body and landscape maps), we were able to pinpoint the participants’ path and experiences in space (the different zones they walked on). Taking the conjunction of the information depicted on the body maps and the interview notes, we were able to derive several insights.

First, the overlap of the two maps allowed us to connect particular body experiences that the participants had to particular points of the landscape, revealing the connection between environment and body experience. For example, we were able to capture and later identify that, for some participants, there were parts of the space that provoked certain sensations independently of the sounds used. Further, the landscape map allowed us to identify the material conditions of the built and natural environment that related to particular body experiences. Overall, the combination of maps allowed us to capture and analyze the existing relationships between the built environment and the body, while also highlighting areas where environmental effects interact with sound conditions (LF and HF). Below, we present emerging insights for the different areas, grouped based on common characteristics.

Natural and Calm Environments. These zones are characterized by natural elements like grass, trees, and earth. Participants report feelings of lightness, femininity, and harmony, often linked with the sensation of softness, protection, and tranquility.

Figure 5: Examples of filled landscape maps: a): P22 (HF). Notes translation: 1. From the recording person walking with boots: carrying more weight. 2. I was walking at my pace. Heavy. Heavier steps. Walking relatively slowly. More stooped. Arms more rigid because of trying to synchronize. Not natural. Feel comfort in the path and the space. 3. Crossed a person. 4. Sound impacted the sensation of the body. 5. Heart rate increased. I lost my pace while crossing a person. 6. A dent on the ground. 7. I heard parrots but I didn't find them in the environment. 8. Straighter *. 9. Conscious of heart rate. 10. Curved. Heavy. b): P13 (LF). 1. The low sound is very oppressive, heavy. Continued more because of inertia. Open steps were difficult for me. A sensation of having the ears blocked. As if my body isn't giving me a response. More self-observed than normal. Question myself at every step. More stable. More curved with the sound. Steps interesting. Changing level. 2. Heavier. 3. The sound doesn't match this place I want to find a space that fits. 4. Frustrated because of not going down. 8. More balance. 9. More comfort closed space matches the sound. 10. Saw birds. 11. Spent less time because of the people and the surface. 12. More closed in general. Less here because of the empty sound. 13. Anxiety. Oppressive sound. Incongruent surfaces. They needed to be harder.

First, this group include Grass/earth (Zone 1 in Figure 4 b): this zone is located between the university campus gate and the passage connecting two buildings, usually no people entering the area. The natural environment and ground material is reported by the participants as providing sensations of embracing nature, often associated with calm and relaxation and a sensation of softness. P17 drew a smile on the face of the body map to show the feeling of relaxation and tranquility, and drew lines going out around the shoulders to show a sensation of being able to fly and lightness, and two short lines under each foot to show the environment or the grass and said, *In the grass I noticed more relaxation, and like the sound went more inside me and I could consider it mine without it being so. Like I could adopt that sound and the nature gave me that tranquility and I could walk the same as the sound. I felt relaxed and like the heaviness from before had changed into nothingness. The environment had a big influence on me especially in the part with nature. The trees, autumn, even the cold seemed pleasing to me because everything was in harmony.* P14 drew a blue line on the body map line with arrows extending outward to indicate opening and wideness of the chest. They drew pink lines on the hips to indicate the legs feeling feminine. The colors were to indicate the difference in gender in the two parts of the body. They also said, *It was strange to hear the sound of heels in the grass, but listening to that gave me the sensation of more movement and being more feminine. The upper part of my body felt more masculine and rigid because I was stretched and straight, but from the legs down I felt more feminine, and my feet were invisible.* P30 drew arrows from the hands to the opposite side of the torso that crossed in the middle to indicate their body

position of the arms being crossed. They also drew lines along the shoulder in front, and from behind arrows going from the back of the shoulder and rounding to the front, showing the position of being more hunched over, they said, *The weather influenced my experience because it was cold. There was also a place with many people and I didn't go there. I liked the grass more than the stone so I tried to walk whenever I could on the grass. Because of the cold I crossed my arms to cover my hands, because normally I don't walk with my arms crossed. I was also more bent because of the cold.*

The second area included in this group is Covered passage with trees (Zone 4): this zone is parallel to zone (3), straight, covered by trees and bordered by columns. People focused more on the details of the experience: they found “limps” in their walking, a memory of a knee injury, more connection with the environment, feeling cold, feeling protected, being observed and memories of childhood that induced happiness. They colored the hands, heart, knee, inguinal area, face and feet areas. P3 drew a blue oval around the full body indicating the feeling of being protected and stated, *As there was a narrow passage with plants that was more secluded and calm, maybe I felt less exposed and more protected,* and P9 drew a line on the belly region, wrote the word “happy” and mentioned, *I felt a strong sensation of happiness in my belly like I'm walking and doing something good.*

In an additional zone, Grass (Zone 5), space and sound conditions interacted in the effects. This is a large and flat grass area, in which participants mentioned spending less time walking on it, and feeling heavy, slow, hearing dry sounds, straight up and happy, protected and calm in relation with the sound condition. P3 said, *I started*

walking in the grass so it was very different because it was like the grass matched the sound more and the sensation of the grass in the feet was more familiar than the stone. But it was very different because (in the other experience with the other sound) it felt very very strange to go on the grass, there was more discoordination. Many participants colored feet and legs.

Structured and Fast-Paced Transit Areas. These zones are with hard surfaces like concrete or tiles. Sensations here are associated with speed, upright posture, confidence, and fluidity. Participants felt a sense of being in their rhythm, with less emotional engagement but more fluid physical movements.

This group includes the Concrete entrance (Zone 2): the area is located next to a building entrance and usually many people pass through it. It transmits sensations of feeling lighter, “robotized” [37], more fluid. People in this area often marked felt changes in feet, hands, shoulders. Moreover, also Concrete passage (Zone 3) is included: this long passage next to Zone 1 is the largest zone. People in this area felt faster, more straight up, found more people passing by and marked chest and feet. P9 drew two body maps: one with a cross on the back to show the feeling of stretching in the back and one with crosses on both the feet to indicate that’s where they felt confident and fluid and said, *I was in my own rhythm, more tranquil and serene. I felt this especially on stretching, especially in my back, and, Here I had a memory of my mother, because there was always an education of how to walk tall, and I felt tall [...] Changing my way of walking made me feel more confident, fast, and fluid.*

In an additional zone, tiled passage (Zone 6), space and sound conditions interacted in the effects. This area is a concrete passage in the center of the space and, in the high frequency condition, the sound was associated with “heels” and gave the sensation of feminine legs and feeling “upright”.

Transitional and Challenging Areas. These zones often involve elevation changes, stairs, or narrow spaces. Participants mention that the sound environment influences their perception of the space, and they report mixed feelings of curiosity, frustration, or tension when navigating these areas.

This category includes Zone 12: concrete floor with steps: this area is on the side and behind the cafeteria, it also includes some dimly lit steps leading to a basement space: these created, for the participants reaching the stairs area, feelings of anxiety and uncertainty. P13 said: *I felt very frustrated not being able to go down the steps because the track ended. I felt like a fish looking for water because closed surrounding were pleasing to me, especially with a deep sound like this. I think your brain also tells you that a sound doesn't correspond with the space, so naturally, at least I, tried to find a space that matched it more and that's why the closed spaces generated in me some kind of relief or rest because they matched what I was listening to.*

In an additional zone, building entrance and steps (Zone 9); space and sound conditions interacted in the effects. Zone (9) is a vast area including some stairs that lead to the cafeteria region. Participants reported feeling a stiff back, and the stairs were considered sometimes curious and engaging because of the change of elevation, or challenging to synchronize to the footstep sounds. This area also contains a rough surface creating unnatural sensations. P13 (during LF) drew circles around the lower legs and chest and shoulders to mark the areas that felt heavier and stuck the body

map on the steps outside the building and said, *In general, the stairs seemed interesting to me in both experiences, and were particularly interesting and strange because of the changes in level. I felt the sound took me a bit to another place or accentuated the sensation, simply because I was changing level. Here I felt a bit heavier with the sound.* Participants often marked the chest, legs, and feet areas.

Interaction with Social and External Contexts. The main zone included in this group is concrete passage next to the cafeteria (Zone 8): this passage is partially covered and shared with the university cafeteria: participants mentioned and marked on the body maps where they felt observed. They usually went faster to avoid the presence of people and/or calling attention. Participant P10 (during LF), near the cafeteria, colored in the head because they had a thought of feeling violated and mentioned, *I thought someone whistled at me, they were very close and it made me feel strange and violated,* and P13 (during HF) said, *Here, I dared to pass closer to more people in comparison to the other experience (LF). It made me feel less anxious I think because the sound made me feel less trapped. I even looked at the people and what they were doing. Earlier they intimidated me more.* P25 (during HF) colored the body map in the back area and reported, *I felt more stretched, the presence of the people made me think about them.* Other participants struggled to focus and avoid thinking about other people. Their sensations were mostly in the legs, head, and chest.

In summary, these zones can be categorized based on their natural, structured, transitional, or social interactions, revealing the complex relationships between the environment, sound conditions, and bodily sensations.

The results above highlight that body maps, as a tool, are highly effective for capturing nuanced and individual bodily experiences in relation to environmental and situational factors. Thanks to the sticker design, including the choice of the size (i.e., big enough for selecting specific body areas), it was possible to extract some information about body areas more often associated with feelings: often stress, tiredness, were located in the head region. Relief covered the head and the back and sometime the chest, while the feet and legs often corresponded to feelings of heaviness. The maps (i.e., landscape and body maps) allowed participants to physically represent how space and sound influenced their sensations, emotions, and movements. This method provided a rich, qualitative understanding of the relationship between the body and the environment, enabling participants to map not only physical sensations like heaviness or relaxation but also emotional states, gendered experiences, and more abstract feelings like those of protection or violation. The use of colors, symbols, and words in the body maps enhanced the specificity of the feedback, allowing for a detailed analysis of localized sensations. The variety of representations, from simple body areas marked with color to more intricate depictions with symbols and arrows, demonstrates the versatility of body maps as a tool for expressing complex, subjective experiences. This approach enabled the researchers to identify and understand various influencing factors for changes in body experiences involved in Study 2, enriching the analysis and interpretation of these phenomena.

Figure 6: Several body maps that were filled in by the participants and placed on the landscape maps.

5 Discussion

In this paper, we presented two approaches for iterating body maps and evaluated them across two studies. Both studies demonstrate the tool’s high flexibility and its adaptability to different research objectives.

5.1 Segmented Body Maps and Body Maps in Context

In HCI, body maps are often used as a design tool in qualitative research [2, 71]. Segmented body maps, as introduced in this work, open new avenues for understanding user experiences with interactive technologies. In particular, analyzing differences across experimental conditions, groups of the population, and the interaction between technological conditions (in our case, sounds) and groups offers a quantitative way to examine body experiences. This approach enables statistical analysis and supports broader generalizations while maintaining a focus on embodied experience.

We acknowledge that bodily sensations are not always easy to localize [38] and that body perception is dynamic [14]. Our tool is specifically designed to capture these sensations in the moment, providing a snapshot of embodied experience during or immediately after interaction. This design opens opportunities for future work in which capturing the evolution of the sensations over time could help track how bodily perception change dynamically in response to ongoing interactions, see [73].

While segmented body maps are not new in quantitative works [48, 53, 60], our hierarchical segmentation of body maps advances these works by offering a tool that provides flexibility in the analysis, enabling both fine-grained examinations of specific body areas and broader overviews of general patterns. This multi-level approach

offers a temporal snapshot that facilitates structured interpretation and generalization of bodily sensations. Researchers can analytically zoom in to conduct fine-grained examinations of specific body areas or zoom out to capture broader patterns. In addition, this dual capability bridges a gap in prior work, where previous segmentation approaches were either absent or lacked hierarchical organization. For example, pain localization studies [48, 56, 58] provide detailed descriptions of the body regions partitioning they chose to employed, but lack the hierarchical structure necessary for multi-level analysis. Similarly, works by [48, 53, 60] examine body sensations at high level (e.g., only writing down where they occur, not their qualities, or their impact), but do not incorporate a segmentation framework iteratively designed and customized using the use case body maps. By contrast, the segmented body maps presented in our work, inspired by anatomical notions [8] and validated experimentally in different populations [13], overcome these limitations. They enable researchers to quantify and compare felt changes in body perception with granularity (e.g., following specific localized areas), allowing for both population-level analysis and individual-level precision. For instance, the tool can reveal how sensory stimulation affects the upper body at a group level while pinpointing specific locations of sensation at the individual level.

Further, segmented body maps provide an adaptable tool that could support novel applications across disciplines. In interaction design, by analyzing how body maps evolve in response to various systems or body-centric systems, designers could uncover rich, nuanced insights into the interplay between body perception and technology. Personalizing segmented body maps to meet specific needs helps with the design of systems that better align with the user’s embodied experience. In other fields, like psychology, cognitive neuroscience, and rehabilitation [53, 60, 64], these maps could

be used to generate generalizable findings, enabling cross-study comparisons and meta-analyses of body perception. By structuring data collection and analysis hierarchically, researchers can explore localized sensations or patterns across broader regions, ensuring both precision and scalability.

The proposed approach of combining body maps and landscape maps builds on prior research, e.g., [26], that contextualizes body maps within situations and narratives that give rise to particular experiences, allowing researchers to visualize intersections of health, culture, and environment. Previous research [71], provides a theoretical backdrop for understanding how and why contextually grounded body maps can serve as efficient tools—for instance, by depicting external environmental factors around the body such as wind or sunlight. These two works call for the need for introducing a tool to add contextual information, locating the body map in space. Our work consolidates this understanding by developing and validating a novel approach to body maps that explicitly introduces environmental mapping through the landscape map. This addition enables researchers to track people's movement and embodied experience within their surrounding space, as explored by [34, 67], and to analyze how external elements influence bodily sensations depicted on the maps. The richness of the results we presented included the possibility of extracting felt sensations not only depending on the experimental conditions (i.e. different sound conditions) but also as shaped by environmental factors and their dynamic interaction with body perception.

The key contribution of these contextual body maps lies in the integration of body maps and the landscape map. Designing body maps integration and use, we were able to examine and capture the connection between felt changes in body sensations to specific physical locations in the space; in turn, allowing us to identify areas in the environment that consistently evoked particular bodily sensations, i.e., feelings of comfort, tension, or relaxation. This integration provided a means to spatially situate bodily experience, revealing systematic correspondences between embodied responses and environmental features. We were also able to study the interplay of sound and space: we observed how the effects of the sound conditions varied across different locations, revealing how environmental context can modulate the effects of sound on body perception. Furthermore, the analysis of the body maps revealed the influence of environmental features: certain environmental features, i.e., the surface material/covering (e.g. grass), were associated with particular feelings, (e.g., comfort and relaxation), suggesting an inherent connection between the environmental features (e.g. natural elements) and body and emotional experiences. These findings extend previous literature [34, 40, 51, 66, 67, 70, 74] by evidencing how embodied responses are co-shaped by material, sensory, and contextual cues. Additionally, we explored how prior experiences and contextual cues (e.g., presence of stairs in an enclosed space) can shape expectations and influence the interpretation of sensory information (e.g., sense of curiosity and exploration). The analysis revealed that body experiences are not static but rather are constantly evolving in response to the interplay of internal and external factors, including auditory cues, environmental context, and prior experiences. The use of colors, symbols, and words, in fact, enabled detailed feedback, highlighting physical sensations,

emotional states, and gendered experiences. The variety in representations, from simple markings to more complex drawings, shows the versatility of body maps in expressing complex, subjective experiences. This underscores their value not only as data collection instruments but also as expressive, interpretive tools in embodied research.

The integration of the two maps (body and landscape maps) was crucial to understanding many underlying aspects that shape bodily experiences. Through the analysis of both, we were able to find that there were parts of the space (i.e., grass/earth (1), concrete entrance (2), concrete passage (3), covered passage with trees (4), and concrete floor with steps) that on their own provoked certain sensations independent of the sound condition. There were some areas (i.e., grass (5), tiled passage (6), concrete passage next to the cafeteria (8), building entrance and steps (9)), in which space and sound conditions interacted. Additionally, there were some areas that on interaction with sound promoted the expected effects (as in previous works [10, 13, 63, 65]): e.g., in the tiled passage (6) the sound of “heels” gave some participants the sensation of feminine legs and of feeling “upright”. In the concrete passage near the cafeteria (8) they also report being “more stretched out”. In contrast, there were areas where the interaction with sound created the opposite effects to those expected: e.g., the grass (5) gave the sensation of feeling heavier, when listening to high frequency sounds. Finally, there were areas where interaction with sound brought new effects not discovered so far: e.g., thinking of the people next to them. Such findings highlight the richness of embodied data obtainable through contextualized body maps and demonstrate how environmental variables can yield distinct bodily interpretations.

The proposed tool and analysis provided a multidimensional understanding of how different spaces and sound conditions impact body perception. This reinforces the utility of body maps in both experiential and research contexts, offering a powerful way to explore and communicate embodied experiences, for example, [4], that uses maps to track and study movement patterns in playgrounds could also gain benefit from the use of body maps, to add personal experience insight to the research. Overall, the combination of segmented and contextual body maps establishes a bridge between quantitative precision and qualitative richness, contributing a methodological framework that is both flexible and empirically grounded.

5.2 Limitations and Future Work

In this work, we proposed a specific segmentation for body maps; however, our tool is highly flexible, enabling users to adjust the level of granularity or apply alternative decisions on the segmentation, as needed for their purposes. For example, our tool can support research on body experiences that focuses on specific localized areas of the body (e.g., the face). In future work, the segmentation could be specifically designed to address these areas (e.g., introducing more subregions for the face and reducing the detail in the rest of the body). Additionally, some participants in Study 1 expressed difficulty marking the lateral and medial areas of the body or lacked a depth dimension to represent their body perception. Segmented body maps in two dimensions fail to fully capture the complexity of three-dimensional perceptions of sensation, especially in regions with a more intricate anatomical structure, like the head, neck,

or torso. Although the lack of depth in our segmented approach could be perceived as a limitation, it is not necessarily the case. While 3D body maps might offer enhanced results, they can also introduce challenges related to visual complexity and participant interpretation [71]. A 2D approach remains accessible and analytically tractable, which is advantageous for large-scale data collection and participant comprehension.

The presented use of body maps captures bodily changes, on the plane of the body, with spatial accuracy. The intricate responses emphasize the need for tailored approaches in technology design and the potential of such a method to address, delineate and eventually target specific body areas. This represents a methodological contribution to future work in HCI and could potentially be linked to other markers, i.e., physiological or behavioral data. The complex nature of this phenomenon may be better understood by utilizing complementary qualitative techniques or machine learning models (e.g., [15, 16]). For example, focus groups and in-depth interviews could provide a more comprehensive understanding of participant's feelings, thoughts, and experiences [2, 71]. As demonstrated by [54], our methodological approach could also integrate details on the intensity of the participants' sensations (through, e.g., different colors), allowing for a more granular analysis of very small and localized features. Integrating multimodal data and intensity encoding [1, 50] could thus enhance the interpretative resolution of future body-map analyses.

The sample size in Study 1, of 84 participants, provides high-quality information from multiple sources and repeated data collection. A larger number of participants could increase the statistical power and reliability of the body maps findings and reveal more patterns or sensible locations in the body areas [55]. With more participants, the results would be more likely representative of each of the populations being studied, increasing the generalizability of the findings. Designing segmented body maps to be simple and intuitive can help make them accessible to a wide audience. Using machine learning models, the approach to segmented body maps could be enhanced by exploring advanced subregion definitions, i.e., dynamic segmentation methods, based on an ensemble decision tree model [24], that adapt to individual anatomical variations. Moreover, there are aspects directly related to the first use case we presented, which could also provide valuable insights for improving practices in other applications. Firstly, with the presented segmentation approach used to extract information from body maps, the different techniques participants used to color them did not impact the results. There are participants that frequently marked the areas of the ears on their body maps, explaining that they did so because they heard the sound through their ears. More detailed instructions could be provided to ensure participants accurately depict body experience changes in their body maps. Secondly, participants often marked areas where they wore straps, bands, or other experiment equipment. In these cases, the marked areas may not correspond to actual feelings induced by the sound manipulation but rather to the presence of the equipment. Adapting the experimental design to minimize the influence of such equipment could mitigate this issue. Lastly, some participants mentioned that certain lines represented specific feelings on the body, i.e., pain, relief, or sensations of muscle extension or contraction. While this qualitative information is important, it was not analyzed through the analysis

of the segmented body maps. Using more qualitative approaches together with the segmented body maps (e.g., interviews), could be beneficial to address this concern.

Moreover, while in this work we focused on segmented maps and body maps in context separately, these tools could also be used together in studies that require quantitative and qualitative understandings of data, further stressing the growing relevance of mixed methods approaches and studies. Integrating both approaches in a single study design could yield a comprehensive account that links measurable bodily patterns with subjective and contextualized interpretations.

The proposed approach to contextualizing body maps in environmental settings identified multiple contextual factors shaping body perception. However, their interrelations were not examined in depth, as the tool was not intended to capture such interactions. We instead focused on the specific aspects of the setting that was utilized, looking at the variables particularly introduced for the proposed study [4]. The factors that we introduced did not include cultural aspects in the population and social relations i.e., the presence of people in the space, cf. [26, 34]. These aspects shape the associations to body sensations [68] and should be not considered universal or static, see [38, 62]. Some participants mentioned these aspects (e.g., the presence of other people) but they were not controlled or specifically examined. The use of the body maps and landscape maps could be extended to also reflect these aspects (e.g., using stickers to include other people in the space); and an analysis focused on the interaction of some of environmental elements could also be included. Future iterations of the tool could thus incorporate social and cultural dimensions of embodiment, enabling analysis of how interpersonal presence and shared environments shape bodily experience; further studies are necessary to understand how these factors interact. When asking the participants to fill in the body maps, if looking for specific body areas, the segmentation could be included in these maps. The maps could also be represented and filled in digitally [7], allowing the possibility to add many body maps in the landscape map, zooming in/out and making the coloring task more effective in extracting the feeling locations in the body. In case the body maps approach is intended for the extraction of qualitative aspects, it could also be possible to include, during the body map filling task, instructions assessing specific features (e.g., posture changes, memories, overall emotional feelings, mood) of the experience that is described. Digital implementations would further enhance interactivity, precision, and longitudinal tracking, offering new possibilities for multimodal data integration and visualization.

Beyond the studies presented here, the mapping framework also lends itself to digital, interactive, and longitudinal applications that extend its methodological reach. In virtual or augmented reality settings, for instance, participants can report sensations in real time as they interact with immersive environments, allowing researchers better track environmental and bodily dynamics [36, 79]. Similarly, mobile or web-based tools for longitudinal tracking have been used to monitor changes in bodily sensations such as pain, fatigue, or proprioception over days or weeks, providing insight into temporal trends and intervention effects [25]. Integration with wearable physiological sensors further enables multimodal approaches, combining subjective mappings of felt experience with objective indicators like heart rate or muscle activation [35]. In

experimental contexts, this can support adaptive systems that modify sound, light, or haptic feedback in response to participants' embodied states [79]. Together, these directions illustrate how the body mapping tool can evolve into an interactive, real-time, and data-rich instrument—capable of linking embodied, affective, and contextual information across scales of time and modality. This perspective reinforces the broader applicability of our methodological contribution, showing how segmented and contextual body maps can integrate with digital systems to study embodied experience dynamically.

In summary, this work introduces a methodological framework combining segmented and contextual body maps, enabling systematic capture and analysis of bodily sensations in relation to environmental or technological factors. This approach balances scalable quantitative analysis with the richness of subjective, situated experience and can be adapted across domains such as HCI, psychology, and rehabilitation. Future research can build on this foundation to explore dynamic, multi-layered representations of the body in context, further integrating physiological, behavioral, and environmental data. In doing so, the proposed methodology contributes to a more comprehensive and empirically grounded understanding of embodiment in interaction.

The body maps we presented expand bodily awareness through interaction, linking fine-grained, localized sensations with broader contextual and environmental influences [2, 30]. Segmented body maps provide a quantifiable way to trace bodily sensations and perceptual changes across participants or conditions, focusing soma design's traditional emphasis, on specific body-area perceptions and sensations. Contextual body maps situate bodily experiences within material, spatial, and social environments, highlighting the mutual shaping of body and context. By integrating landscape and body maps, this approach extends soma design, allowing researchers to document how environmental factors influence somatic perception.

5.3 Novelty, Relevance and Contributions

Segmented body maps serve as a valuable tool for quantitative data analysis. This methodological approach of body maps can uncover new insights into body perception or emotional experience patterns and body areas for further investigation. The integration of body maps with environmental factors is a novel approach. By focusing on variables specific to the study setting, the research opens new possibilities to understand how environmental factors (i.e., spatial conditions, other people in the space) impact physical and emotional experiences. For researchers adopting quantitative methods [7, 48, 53, 60], the proposed segmented body maps provide a finer-grained representation of bodily sensations, enabling more precise analysis of how interventions or stimuli modulate body perception. For those researchers adopting qualitative or soma-based approaches [44, 47, 73, 78], the contextual body maps situate bodily experiences within the environments where they emerge, emphasizing how spatial, material, and social factors co-create felt experience. Research in soma design, e.g., [30, 59], could integrate our body maps in their processes, with the objective of both tracking sensations in the body and to situate the body in space, thereby deepening embodied awareness and informing more nuanced design interactions.

Our work evolves the research of body maps in the TEI community, and more broadly in HCI, and provides an inspiration to the interaction design community exploring body maps as a research tool [2, 26, 28, 71]. We offer new perspectives on how to integrate quantitative methods and contextual elements into body maps to build on research that captures the richness and nuances of body experiences.

6 Conclusion

In this work, we present an innovative approach to body maps by using segmented maps and body maps together with landscape maps. Segmented body maps allow for detailed analysis of localized sensations, enhancing the ability to compare findings across studies, and providing a flexible tool to investigate user reactions to technology. The integration with landscape maps contextualizes bodily experiences, shedding light on how factors like sound and environmental elements shape emotional and physical responses. We aim for our contributions to serve as a valuable and motivating foundation for advancing body maps as a research tool in HCI.

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